

A Study of the Relationship of Major Variables of Commerce and Learners Development

Dr. Bhuvnesh Kumar

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Commerce DPBS (PG) College, Anoopshahr, Bulandshahr, Uttar Pradesh, India

Corresponding author- **Dr. Bhuvnesh Kumar**

E-mail: kumarbh75@yahoo.com

Abstract:

The present research study was design to investigate the relationship of major variables of commerce and learners development of graduate students of University of Delhi. The variables under consideration were related to commerce (Sale, Purchase, Production & Management) and learner's developmental values (Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values). The data were collected from 120 students through self made questionnaire from different college students of University of Delhi using the simple random sampling technique. For analysis, correlation analysis, and descriptive analysis were used. The findings revealed that major variables of commerce are related to learner's developmental values and significantly contribute in the social, cultural, economical and personnel development of graduate students.

Keywords: Sale, Purchase, Production, Management, Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical Development and Personnel Development

Introduction

Education may be liberal or it may be special. Now a days there are three faculties in higher education namely arts, commerce and science. Young people, now a days, are generally guided by lucrative aims. Their main desire is to earn money and become rich. Very few aspire for knowledge for the sake of knowledge-the aim for the older generations. Business education offers good prospects for the ambitious person. Many of them join commerce colleges or take admission in commerce with the aim of getting good jobs. Commerce is that part of business which is concerned with the exchange of goods and services and includes all those activities which directly or indirectly facilitate that exchange. Economic activities and aims dominate the minds of modern men. Business, commerce and industries are important branches of economic activities. Industries are said to be the backbone of national economy. Trade or business follows the flag. The Englishmen came to India as traders and ultimately became the masters. Commerce is at the moment a promising subject as a whole. In the present day world, almost every human activity is related with economy, whether in the shape of trade and industry or commerce and banking. Any concern which has transaction of money, a commerce graduate has his footing there. Secondly, the related fields of commerce are many and varied. Commerce is a branch of business. It is concerned with the exchange of goods and services. It includes all those activities, which directly or indirectly facilitate that exchange. On the basis of the importance and utility of the commerce variables the investigator was excited to find the relationship among the commerce

and learners developmental values. So investigator conducted this study to know the facts about it.

1. Review of the Related Literature

Commerce education is described as an ordered endeavor to mould the citizens for enterprising and managing business competently and fruitfully. The principal intent of commerce education is to endow with skilled manpower mandatory by the business strata in different sections. It aims at humanizing the quality and productivity of personnel in business. Thus, commerce education is concerned not only with the development of vocational skills in purely economic terms but also with social usefulness. But often, the prevailing modes adopted to materialize the goals of commerce curriculum are far from satisfactory. A challenge has been put here to bring some of them which are closely associated with the present study. A number of studies have been carried out to identify and analyze the numerous factors that related to learners development and various variables of commerce.

Paul (2012) did a research study on the area of challenge based learning strategy and stated that Challenge Based Learning strategy asserts students learn more and are more through active engagement when they are solving problems, especially authentic, real world one. The study investigates the Effectiveness of Challenge Based Learning on the Academic Achievement of commerce students at higher secondary level. The investigator found that Challenge Based Learning is an effective instructional strategy on the Academic Achievement of commerce students at higher secondary level. Also this strategy is effective in developing skills of problem solving, creative thinking and decision making.

Roshan, Ara (2011) presented the sum up of the proceedings of a workshop held in Jammu & Kashmir, Board of School Education on the significance of commerce education. The workshop highlighted the need for making student centered and stresses free commerce curriculum and focused the need for restructuring the existing commerce curriculum when the entire business world is undergoing significant changes requiring advanced study and research.

Krishnamurthy and Amutha (2011) conducted a study entitled on “Higher secondary student’s achievement in commerce in relation to their emotional intelligence”. The study concluded that the higher secondary school student’s achievement in commerce is at moderate level. Further; gender, locality and type of school make significant difference in the achievement of commerce students. But religion, family size and family income make no significant difference. Similarly with regard to emotional intelligence, entire and sub samples fall in the category of average level of emotional intelligence. Gender, locality and religion causes significant difference in the emotional intelligence level and type of school, family size and family income cause to significant difference. But higher secondary school commerce student’s achievement is significantly related to their emotional intelligence for both entire and sub sample wise.

Sajikumar (2011) did a study on “Effectiveness of certain behavior modification models on achievement in commerce among students at higher secondary level”. The major findings of the study holds that under appropriate conditions, a sizeable portion of the population can be brought to a level of achievement in the subject, interest in the subject and attitude towards the subject. The study suggested that the teachers can tailor instruction to the needs of most of the students in the classroom by employing behavior modification models in the classroom. For this, it is desirable that the teachers should have a fresh outlook at their teaching approach in terms of behavior modification models.

Awi, Asnaini (2008) conducted a study on “Relationship between teacher’s knowledge of the commerce learning experience and evaluation and the teachers’ management on the implementation of the commerce in secondary schools”. The results showed that teachers’ level of knowledge of commerce learning experience and evaluation is moderate; meanwhile the level of the commerce’s instruction and its implementation management is moderate. The results revealed that no significant relationship exist between teachers’ knowledge of the learning experience and the implementation of the instruction based on the aspects of management of teaching, classroom management and test management.

Arumugarajan (2008) engaged in a study on “Abstract reasoning of commerce students studying in school”. The study found that the level of abstract reasoning ability of higher secondary commerce students is moderate. The level of achievement of higher secondary commerce students is average. Also the study realized that there is significant difference between plus one and plus two commerce students with reference to abstract reasoning.

Obul, Reddy(2007) presented a paper on “Revitalizing commerce education” highlighted the broad objectives of liberal education with the aim of fostering students with an attitude of objective enquiry, understanding of the society, social change, problems of human relationships, human and social implications of technological change, developing a capacity to appreciate the higher values of life and the like. These objectives are taken as implied in the case of business education also. Education should be a three-fold process of imparting knowledge, developing skills, inculcating proper attitudes and values towards life and society in general

It is obvious from the review of the related research studies that major variables of commerce and social, economic, cultural and economical development values have not been studied all together. Therefore, the study is unique and original.

2. Statement of the Problem

The investigator stated the study as-

“A Study of the Relationship of Major Variables of Commerce and Learners Development”

3. Objectives of the Study

1. To know the relationship among Sale and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values
2. To know the relationship among Purchase and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values
3. To know the relationship among Production and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values
4. To know the relationship among Management and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

4. Hypotheses of the Study

The investigator formulated the following null-hypotheses to conduct this research:

1. There is no significant relationship between Sale and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values
2. There is no significant relationship between Purchase and Social Development, Cultural

Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

3. There is no significant relationship between Production and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values
4. There is no significant relationship between Management and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

5. Variables of the Study

5.1. Variables related to Commerce

Sale: The exchange of goods or services for an amount of money or its equivalent; the act of selling: The sale of such a nice house should be easy.

Purchase: To obtain ownership of a security or other asset in exchange for money or value. also called buy.

Production: The processes and methods used to transform tangible inputs (raw materials, semi-finished goods, subassemblies) and intangible inputs (ideas, information, knowledge) into goods or services. Resources are used in this process to create an output that is suitable for use or has exchange value.

Management: The organization and coordination of the activities of a business in order to achieve defined objectives. Management is often included as a factor of production along with, machines, materials, and money. According to the management guru Peter Drucker (1909-2005), the basic task of management includes both marketing and innovation.

5.2. Variables related to Developmental Values

Social Developmental values: Social development involves learning the values, knowledge and skills that enable children to relate to others effectively and to contribute in positive ways to family, school and the community. This kind of

learning is passed on to children directly by those who care for and teach them, as well as indirectly through social relationships within the family or with friends, and through children's participation in the culture around them. Through their relationships with others and their growing awareness of social values and expectations, children build a sense of who they are and of the social roles available to them. As children develop socially, they both respond to the influences around them and play an active part in shaping their relationships.

Cultural Developmental Values: The totality of socially transmitted behavior patterns, arts, beliefs, institutions, and all other products of human work and thought. These patterns, traits, and products considered as the expression of a particular community, period, class, or population: Edwardian culture; Japanese culture; the culture of poverty.

Economical developmental Values: The worth of a good or service as determined by people's preferences and the tradeoffs they choose to make given their scarce resources, or the value the market places on an item. Economic value is represented by the maximum amount a consumer is willing to pay for an item in a free market economy, or the amount of time an individual will sacrifice waiting to obtain a government-rationed good in a socialist economy. In contrast, market value represents the minimum amount a consumer will pay. Economic value thus often exceeds market value.

Personnel Development Values: Personnel values are those traits we see as worth aspiring to, and that define our character.

6. Sample of the Study

The investigator was taken the sample from the University of Delhi to conduct this valuable study. 120 students were taken as a sample from different colleges of Delhi University. The sample was chosen with the help of stratified random sampling technique.

Table No-1: Showing Sample of the Study

Name of the College	Sample	
	Girls	Boys
Sri Ram College of Commerce, DU	15	15
Guru Nanak College, DU	15	15
Maharaja Agrasain College, DU	15	15
Shyam Lal College, DU	15	15
Total	60	60

7. Tool & Techniques

The investigator used the self made questionnaire to collect the data from the students. Since accuracy of measures, validity deals with the question as to whether a measure in fact measuring what it purports to measure. So, investigator checked the reliability and validity of the questionnaire before administer the tool.

8. Data Collection

The investigator had decided to administer the tests on the students of different colleges affiliated to University of Delhi. The investigator personally selected 04 (No. of colleges) colleges and met the principals one day ahead to seek their permission and time to administer the test items. He even met the target group of principals to inform them about the exercise to be undertaken and the purpose to

meet. Next day, it made them ready for all practical requirements. After take the permission, first day of the visit to respective colleges, every principal was informed about the purpose of the study. A rapport was established, and a well conductive atmosphere was created. The data collection work was started by the investigator as per suitability and availability of students. The researcher provided a questionnaire to every student in a booklet form. Questionnaire was given to students after them into confidence that the information's so generated would be kept confidential and would not be used for any other purpose. After filling the personal details, the students were requested to read the instructions carefully and were enabled to understand the questions by explaining the example quoted by author.

9. Data Analysis

As mentioned earlier the problem of research was "A Study of the Relationship of Major Variables of Commerce and Learners Development". The essential objectives' underlying this study was to investigate whether relationship of major variables

of commerce were in any way related to learners development. To study this, certain hypotheses of relationship were formulated. To test these hypotheses relevant data on each of these variables were collected, which have been analyzed and discussed. To test the hypotheses, relevant data were collected from the students of different colleges affiliated to University of Delhi. All the scores on the tool have been reproduced in the master sheet. The results have been drawn and discussed hypothesis wise. Each hypothesis was tested and analyzed to achieve the formulated objectives

Objective-1: To know the relationship between Sale and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

In order to achieve this objective, hypotheses no. 1 was formulated. This section presents the results of the analysis pertaining to this hypothesis.

Hypothesis-1: There is no significant relationship between Sale and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

Table 4.1

Correlation among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Sale

Variables	N	'r' value	Null Hypothesis
Social Developmental values	120	0.82	Rejected
Cultural Developmental values			
Economical Developmental values			
Personnel Developmental values			
Sale	120		

In the same sequence as seen in the table, the significant relationship among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Sale. The developmental values and sale were found correlation at 0.05 level of significance ('r' 0.82). Hence, the null-hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. It seems Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Sales are having positive correlation.

Objective-2: To know the relationship between Purchase and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

In order to achieve this objective, hypotheses no. 2 was formulated.

Hypothesis-2: There is no significant relationship between Purchase and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values.

Table 4.2

Correlation among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Purchase

Variables	N	'r' value	Null Hypothesis
Social Developmental values	120	0.91	Rejected
Cultural Developmental values			
Economical Developmental values			
Personnel Developmental values			
Purchase	120		

A quick look on the table exhibited that the significant relationship among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and

Purchase. The developmental values and purchase were found correlation at 0.05 level of significance ('r' 0.91). Hence, the null-hypothesis was rejected at

0.05 level of significance. It seems Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Purchasing are positive related.

Objective-3: To know the relationship and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical

development, Personnel Developmental Values and Production

Hypothesis-3: There is no significant relationship among Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values and Production

Table 4.3

Correlation among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Sale

Variables	N	'r' value	Null Hypothesis
Social Developmental values	120	1.22	Accepted
Cultural Developmental values			
Economical Developmental values			
Personnel Developmental values			
Production	120		

In the same sequence as seen in the table, the significant relationship did not find among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Production. The developmental values and production were not found correlation at 0.05 level of significance ('r' 1.22). Hence, the null-hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. It seems Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Productions are no correlated.

Objective-4: To know the relationship between Management and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values

Hypothesis-4: There is no significant relationship among Production and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values.

Table 4.4

Correlation among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and management

Variables	N	'r' value	Null Hypothesis
Social Developmental values	120	0.88	Rejected
Cultural Developmental values			
Economical Developmental values			
Personnel Developmental values			
Management	120		

A quick look on the table exhibited that the significant relationship among Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Management. The developmental values and purchase were found correlation at 0.05 level of significance ('r' 0.88). Hence, the null-hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. It seems Social, Cultural, Economical, Personnel Developmental Values and Management are positive related.

10. Findings of the Study

On the behalf of analysis of data, the investigator concluded the following findings:-

1. The investigator found the positive relationship among Sale and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values. Because students are use this variable in their daily life and have well knowledge about this variable of

commerce. It means sale variable of commerce is very helpful to develop the values in learners.

2. Purchasing is most correlated variable of commerce with Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values. It means students are well known about the purchasing.
3. The relationship did not find among Production and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values. It means students did not correlate directly with production.
4. Management and Social Development, Cultural Development, Economical development and Personnel Developmental Values are highly correlated with each others. It means management is very helpful to develop the values in learners.

Recommendations for Further Research

1. This study is limited to students of University of Delhi. It can conduct at other students of different region.
2. This study is limited to small sample. It can be explored on a larger sample.
3. Other studies can be conduct on the different variables of commerce.

References:

1. Aripin, R., Mahmood, Z., Rohaizad, R., Yeop, U., & Anuar, M. (2003). Students' learning styles and academic performance. 22nd Annual SAS Malaysia Forum, 15th July 2008, Kuala Lumpur Convention Center, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.
2. Arumugarajan (2008). "Abstract reasoning of commerce students studying in school". *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology and Psychopedagogy*, 1(1), 43 – 66.
3. Awi, A. (2008). "Relationship between teacher's knowledge of the commerce learning experience and evaluation and the teachers' management on the implementation of the commerce in secondary schools". *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 78(3), 499 – 507.
4. Diaz, A. L. (2003). Personal, family, and academic factors affecting low achievement in secondary schools. *Electronic Journal of Research in Educational Psychology and Psychopedagogy*, 1(1), 43 – 66.
5. Durden, G. C., & Ellis, L. V. (1995). The effects of attendance on student learning in principles of economics. *American Economic Review*, 85(2), 343–346.
6. Heinesen, E. (2010). Estimating class-size effects using within-school variation in subject-specific classes. *The Economic Journal*, 120(545), 737 – 760.
7. <http://kalyan-city.blogspot.in/2011/03/what-is-commerce-meaning-and-importance.html>
8. <https://www.kidsmatter.edu.au/families/about-friendship/social-development/socialdevelopment-children%E2%80%99s-social-development>
9. Krishnamurthy and Amutha (2011). "Higher secondary student's achievement in commerce in relation to their emotional intelligence". *Journal of Education for Business*, 73 (5), 302 – 307.
10. Kumar, S. (2011). "Effectiveness of certain behavior modification models on achievement in commerce among students at higher secondary level". *Journal of Economic Education*, 25(2), 99 – 119.
11. Omrod, J. E. (2008). *Educational psychology: developing learners*. Sixth Edition. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Education.
12. Park, K. H., & Kerr, P. M. (1990). Determinants of academic performance: A multinomial logit approach. *Journal of Economic Education*, 21(2), 101–111.
13. Paul (2012). "The Effectiveness of Challenge Based Learning on the Academic Achievement of commerce students at higher secondary level." *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 1(1), 13 – 28.
14. R, Arya. (2011). "A workshop Proceedings Jammu & Kashmir, Board of School Education on the significance of commerce education." Jammu & Kashmir, India.
15. Reddy, O. (2007). "Revitalizing commerce education." *Journal of Economic Education*.
16. Zimmerman, B. J., Bandura, A., & Martinez-Pons, M. (1992). Self-motivation for academic attainment: The role of self-efficacy beliefs and personal goal setting. *American Educational Research Journal*, 29(3), 663 – 676.